

Public Health Arrangements and Norms of Indian Public Health Standards in India

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Abstract: This paper estimates the shortfall of various types of public health workforce in India. The Government of India has adopted the *Indian Public Health Standards* (IPHS) by putting aside the erstwhile provisions of the *Bureau of Indian Standards* to promote the public health sector of India. *Government of India* has acknowledged the difficulties in implementing various provisions of the *Bureau of Indian Standards*. One of the reasons included the high cost and while migrating to IPHS, it was aimed to upgrade the existing health facilities, meet the workforce requirements, and ensure the all range of services. However, still deficiencies persisted in numbers of the required and existed numbers of the public health workforce.

Identification of gaps in terms of number of facilities, workforce, and logistics was involved with a lot of numerical analysis based upon various data such as '*Rural Health Survey Bulletins*', '*MIS on NRHM*', '*Census 2011*', and '*Indian Public Health Standards*'. It could be established that there was a shortfall of almost 100914 Health Sub Centers or HSCs, 17399 Primary Health Centers or PHCs, 5728 Community Health Center or CHCs and 1476 Sub Divisional Hospital or First Referral Units or FRUs in the country. Therefore, it could be said that almost 40.7 percent, 42.36 percent, 55.77 percent, and 60.99 percent populations in the country were not covered by any Health Sub Centers, Primary Health Centers, Community Health Centers and Sub Divisional Hospital or First Referral Units respectively. Additionally, there were huge gaps in the workforce, including specialists, doctors, and other medical and paramedical staff especially nurses and technicians.

The country even faced tremendous problems even in implementing the norms of the Indian Public Health Standards despite the dilution of various provisions of the Bureau of Indian Standards. The large vulnerability persisted in the country's public health sector could be attributed to those deficiencies.

Key words: *Indian Public Health Standards; Bureau of Indian Standards; Public Health Work Force; Public Health Facilities.*

Introduction:

The launch of the National Rural Health Mission or NRHM in the year 2005 as a flagship initiative of the Government of India, it was expected that the public health sector would be put on the right course. Even it was adopted as a matter of policy to implement the various provisions of the Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS).^[1] However, still a large gap persisted in terms of numbers of public health facilities and workforce, required and existed in the country even in those terms of the IPHS.

The Indian public health system found deficient in terms of both quality of services and adequacy of coverage. The chief reasons could be easily identified as the deficient work force, logistics, and infrastructure. To overcome such deficiencies the Government of India in the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare had set certain norms under the Indian Public Health Standards or IPHS. The earlier draft format of IPHS was released in the year 2006 while revising draft was released in the year 2010. IPHS provided and guided the norms following which public health facilities would be established and workforce and logistics would be provided. IPHS has adopted a population based criteria for establishment of new public health facilities as well as upgrading the existing facilities. Even IPHS all set the norms for range of particular services to

be made available in various types of the public health facilities and range of services at each health facility starting from health sub centers or HSCs to District Hospitals or DHs. Norms for Primary Health Centers or PHCs, Community Health Centers or CHCs, Sub Divisional Health Centers also outlined in the draft guidelines^{[2] [3] [4] [5]}. However, still all those norms were referred as draft and waiting a final outcome in this regard and mostly certain tentativeness remained associated with the implementation of the IPHS.

The IPHS clearly stated that health care delivery in India would be envisaged at three levels namely primary, secondary, and tertiary. At primary level HSCs and PHCs would be set up every 5000 and 30000 populations, respectively in the plains, however, this population limit was respectively 3000 and 20000 for hilly/ tribal and hard to reach areas. The secondary level of health care essentials included Community Health Centers or CHCs, constituting the First Referral Units (FRUs) and the District hospitals. The CHCs were needed to be upgraded to provide referral health care for cases from the primary level and for cases in need of specialist care approaching the centre directly. Each CHC therefore, required catering, health services to approximately 80,000 populations in tribal / hilly areas and 1, 20,000 populations in plain areas. It was also outlined that each CHC would be a 30-bedded

hospital providing specialist care in medicine, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Surgery and Pediatrics. The launch of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) gave the opportunity to have a fresh look at their functioning. At the tertiary level regional, state level specialty and super specialty hospitals were to be developed, although no guidelines yet outlined for tertiary level under IPHS.

The problem:

The various data and inventory of accomplishments put forward by the government through various data could not be entirely reliable. There were serious doubts and objections about most of those data presented by the government periodically through the executive summary. Even all those data put forward by various agencies such as National Family Health Survey, Multi Indicator Surveys, and sources could not be entirely relied upon. Most surprisingly, all such data agencies never made a distinction between the respective contributions of the public health sector and the private health sector. The private health sector in India was massively developed and has almost 80 percent stake in the total health expenditure of the country.

In addition, the coverage of various public health facilities never corresponded to the population norms prescribed. Even the number of facilities and work force required were though assessed, however, it was not possible to arrange those workforce because of the limited capacities of medical and paramedical educational institutions. [6] National Rural Health Survey (RHS) was periodically accomplished by the Ministry of Health and FW, GOI easily provided an estimate of the deficient numbers of public health facilities and workforce.

The gaps in infrastructure, workforce, and logistics needed to be fresh and independently analyzed. It would be evident that NRHM implemented both in urban and rural areas since it's been earlier planned to launch a different health mission for urban areas, however, there was a delay in the launch of the *National Urban Health Mission* (NUHM). The urban areas largely remained uncovered for substantial periods. Now both the urban and rural health missions were put under the umbrella of the *National Health Mission* (NHM).

The problem of 'timing' in the public health sector of India could be significant. The term *timing* may be referred as a condition whereby infrastructure, logistics, and the workforce would be occurring simultaneously in a spatial and temporal manner. Therefore, the lack of *timing* emerged as a major public health problem and in absence of timing public health services could not ensure in a regular and qualitative manner. An infrastructure, logistics and workforce without one another would be a valuable waste. Therefore, the public health sector of India was suffering from the issues of *timing*.

The temporary or permanent breakdown of services were mainly due to lack or absence of any one or two or even all three basic components either in the permanent or temporary manner. An analysis of several breakdown situations has revealed that all three components required to run the public health delivery system round the clock such as workforce, infrastructure, and logistics not available simultaneously. They're several examples that if doctors available, then there

no supportive staffs, if both doctors and supportive staffs available then there no infrastructure or logistics.

The word '*timing*' could be also significant for the readiness or preparedness of the public health sector in India in order to deliver the desired health services at any point of time and anywhere. The concept of '*timing*' could apply differently under varied situation. The word '*timing*' could have a different interpretation in case of public health services or medical services separately, but the moment we assume that medical services being also a part of any public health care system, it applied to both. The casual and temporary breakdown of the health services resulted due to the sudden emergence of deficiencies either in infrastructure, work force or logistics whereas the permanent breakdown emerged due to non-expansion of coverage based on population norms suggested by IPHS as the population remained uncovered.

Methods and Materials:

The study was involved with a lot of numbness and data triangulations. Additionally, a survey of almost 50 Health Sub Centers (HSCs), 34 Primary Health Centers (PHCs), and 10 District Hospitals (DHs) in states including Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal were conducted. A comprehensive gap analysis for each state was conducted based on 2011 population to estimate the number of existing and required health facilities and work force in the country according to the norms of IPHS. The decadal growth rates of the population were also considered while calculating the total population for a particular year. The gaps were then analyzed based on the various norms provided by the *Indian Public Health Standards*. Then the existing workforce and infrastructure were identified from the various sources such as periodical "Rural Health Surveys" [6] and "MIS on NRHM for the periods of study." [7] Finally, the inferences were drawn after corroborating the primary and various secondary data. The viewpoints, observations, and suggestions put forward in various *Common Review Missions* (CRMs) [8] were also considered.

Results:

It could be evidence that there a huge gap persisted even after more than 11 years of NRHM and almost 4 years of NUHM. The gap in the number of health facilities required and existing identified and maintained in tabular form in **Table-1**; therefore, you may please see in **Table-1**. It would be evident from **Table-1** that there was a shortfall of approximately 100914 HSCs, 17399 PHCs, 5728 CHCs and 1476 Sub Divisional or FRUs in the country. Such data said that approximately 40.7 percent, 42.36 percent, 55.77 percent, and 60.99 percent populations in the country, not covered by any Health Sub Centers, Primary Health Centers, Community Health Centers and Sub Divisional Hospital or First Referral Units respectively.

The required number of different kinds of work force has been estimated and presented in tabular form in **Table-2** and; therefore please see in **table-2**. However, the number of existing workforce could not be retrieved despite all efforts. This was mainly because that employees related data was not properly maintained at the respective levels of the district,

state, or the centre. There was not any dedicated human resources management and information system and it was very difficult to know who did what and how. There was an urgent need of maintaining digital files of each and every employee so that they may be accessed easily. It was due to several limitations the data could not retrieve from all over the country. Even Rural Health Survey bulletin could not provide information on all kinds of existing employee. Number of existing employees have been presented in tabular form in **table-3**; therefore see in **table-3**.

Case studies and survey of various health facilities revealed that there were numerous incidents across the country, but more in EAG States where infrastructure and logistics were not used due to lack of adequate work force. At several places in EAG states, though the buildings and logistics created, however, not used to some or great extent due to lack of adequate work force. Several health centers existed without woman doctors or gynecologists. Many health facilities were suffering due to lack of surgeons and specialist doctors at the district and sub district level hospitals. Therefore, it would be proper to ascertain availability of medical and paramedical staff prior to plan for up gradation and creation of infrastructure and logistics for health facilities. Only those facilities needed to be upgraded for which all kinds of work force may be ensured. The crisis of doctors and paramedics was very deep and so much so that in many states, doctors were posted in mobile manner and getting deployed to serve at different locations. This puts extra burden on the doctors that adversely affected their performance.

The planning process under NRHM did not correspond to the availability of the work force. There was a tremendous lack of retention and performance based incentives and disincentives. Doctors migrated out of the public health sector on large scale causing a great brain drain because such migration knowledge associated with a particular person also lost. Certain special provisions required for the longevity of the attachment period of the workforce. In some states, though such provisions existed, whereby doctors required extending services in rural areas for a certain period, despite many doctors not willing posted in rural areas and so much, so that they usually persuaded authorities to keep themselves posted at locations near to urban centers. This could reason that in several states, urban health facilities had many doctors than it required, whereas in rural areas their number hugely fallen short than required. In any primary health centers, there were hardly any residential quarters for staff. Moreover, it was not possible having children to live with family because there were no proper schools and other civil amenities. Most areas were not electrified and workforce hesitated in getting posted or deployed in any rural, hilly, or difficult to reach and live areas. Moreover, there was not a handful of reputed doctors in the system. Although some reputed doctors were here and there, however, they OPDs were full of crowds and they attended them without any additional benefits. The multi skilling of doctors was though favored under the NRHM however, the same was not so effective in many facilities. Until the adequate work force made available, planning and investments for new health installations would not be logical and it would make a waste of public funds. Definitely numerical inadequacy of the

work force was causing shadows on the expansion of coverage of the public health services in several states of India.

The gap in infrastructure and logistics could fill at a given point of time, but a gap in work force medical and paramedical staff emerged as one of the most challenging factors. Several efforts were initiated or were in pipeline to fulfill the gap of the work force in the country. It could not be possible for the medical and paramedical institutions in India to fulfill the gap of doctors and paramedics for the next fifty years due to paucity of resources and capacities. Therefore, it was also planned to introduce new cadres in the medical field, namely '*Bachelor of Rural Health*'^[9] which expected to enable the services of doctors in rural areas in short time. Such workforce would be refereed as rural doctors after an education of 3 years. The lack of workforce has resulted in outsourcing of various public health services. In the name of outsourcing and public private partnerships the public health of the country was made costly and expensive.

The number of OPD cases witnessed phenomenal growth in recent years, but health services could not limit to just OPD services. The lack of workforce, especially doctors and paramedics could not level overnight and it required time because the capacity of the country in producing doctors and paramedics so limited^[10]. This prevented the expansion process of the health coverage and caused a lack of *timing*. Until and unless required *timing* obtained the public health, services would remain vulnerable.

It was also found that certain states were not able to extend the number of health installations according to their population, though that was required accomplished as per IPHS. Thus, the coverage of health services in the public sector never adequate in those states. It was found under the study that the public health services in India have not improved in percentage terms since independence as it was still around 33 percent. In some states, especially poor performing states the gap was so substantial that it required some special intervention in the form of sustained administrative efforts at various levels of administration.

It was a conservative estimate by this study that there was a shortfall of almost 0.7 million doctors in the country and this shortfall was so high that it's not possible to expand the coverage of health services to the tune of IPHS. This particular status has resulted in a situation where large population remained uncovered or poorly serviced across the country, but the problem could be more visible in those EAG states or high focused states of the country. It was almost evident that this huge gap could not be leveled in the near future either. The country since independence able to produce 0.6 million doctors approximately and filling the gap of more than 0.6 million doctors would consume further fifty years. Therefore, a rational concept brought forwards by the health planners to introduce a new cadre of doctors in the country namely '*Bachelor of Rural Health*'. It proposed that under this cadre, doctors would complete education within 3-4 years and their services might available in short span of time. Nevertheless, this idea generated widespread demonstrations and strikes, especially by Indian Medical Association, which went all out opposing this new cadre in the country's health sector.

Multi Skilling could help to prevent any unwanted disruption in the services.^[11] Multi Skilling training of work force such as doctors, paramedics, and managerial staff was one of the most focused approaches under NRHM to tackle the issue of lack of work force. Nevertheless, multi Skilling also had extremely limited usages and thus any extraordinary could not achieve by multi Skilling. Also, though multi Skilling appeared more prudent in developed states, but it was not such in EAG states. Under multi Skilling, a doctor or paramedics trained in performing that kind of job, which could not expect from them in ordinary situation, but the extraordinary situation required extraordinary approaches. However, multi Skilling was useful and required despite it was a temporary arrangement and not any solution.

Conclusion:

The concept of *timing* for a public health sector used to be occurring simultaneously of all three factors work force, infrastructure, and logistics all the time. With huge gap persisting as per IPHS in terms of number of required and existing health facilities and work force the public health coverage could not said adequate. The level of adequacy and coverage could much deficient as shown in the Rural Health Surveys. Either IPHS had been just a crude documents or

certain deficiency existed in terms of implementing IPHS by the authorities. Confusing data shown by the Ministry of Health and FW GOI, which required to make more perfect.

Government must assess availability of work force first try to produce and acquire them first and then they opt for expansion or upgrading of health facilities or creation of new health facilities as per IPHS. Thus, IPHS just remained an unimplemented in the country. It required investing, creating work force first, and then planning for expansion and up gradation of health facilities according to the available work force. Infrastructure, logistics, and work force in the absence of each other could prove a precious waste of resources of a poor country. Unfortunately, NRHM not able to do anything in this regard in order to produce, acquire, groom, and retain a work force for the country’s public health sector.

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Declaration:

Author declares that there are no any conflicting interests of any kind.

Table-1: Deficiencies in number of facilities

S. No.	India/States/UTs	Total Population 2011	Health sub centers		Primary health centers		Community health centers		Sub-District hospitals		District hospitals	
			R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**	R*	E**
01	INDIA	1210193422	247943	147029	41072	23673	10269	4541	2420	944	644	645
02	J & K	12548926	4183	1907	627	375	15	85	25	00	22	22
03	HP#	6856509	2285	2071	343	449	86	73	14	36	12	12
04	Punjab	27704236	5540	2950	923	446	231	129	55	35	20	20
05	Chandigarh	1054686	211	16	35	00	9	02	2	00	1	1
06	Uttarakhand #	10116752	3372	1765	506	239	126	55	20	18	13	18
07	Haryana	25353081	5070	2444	845	441	211	107	51	25	21	21
08	NCT of Delhi	16753235	3350	41	558	08	140	00	33	49	9	18
09	Rajasthan	68621012	13724	11487	2287	1504	572	368	137	12	33	33
10	Uttar Pradesh	199581477	3991	20521	6652	3692	1663	515	399	00	75	134
11	Bihar	103804637	20760	9696	3460	1863	865	70	208	40	38	36
12	Sikkim#	607688	202	147	30	24	8	00	1	00	4	04
13	Arunachal Pradesh#	1382611	461	286	69	97	17	48	3	00	16	14
14	Nagaland#	1980602	660	396	99	126	25	21	4	00	11	11
15	Manipur#	2721756	907	420	136	73	34	16	5	01	9	07
16	Mizoram#	1091014	364	370	54	57	14	09	2	2	8	8
17	Tripura#	3671032	1224	627	183	79	46	11	7	11	4	2
18	Meghalaya#	2964007	988	405	148	109	37	29	6	1	7	10
19	Assam	31169272	6233	4604	1039	856	260	108	62	13	27	22
20	West Bengal	91347736	18269	10356	3045	909	761	348	183	45	19	16
21	Jharkhand	32966238	6593	3958	1099	330	275	188	66	6	24	21
22	Orissa	41947358	8389	6688	1398	1279	349	231	84	22	30	32
23	Chhattisgarh	25540196	5108	4776	851	716	213	143	51	17	18	17
24	Madhya Pradesh	72597565	14519	8869	2420	1155	605	333	145	56	50	50
25	Gujarat	60383628	12076	7274	2013	1096	503	290	121	00	26	00
26	Daman & Diu	242911	48	26	8	03	2	02	1	0	2	2
27	D & N Haveli	342853	68	50	11	06	3	01	1	0	1	1

28	Maharashtra	112372972	22474	10580	3745	1816	936	365	225	80	35	23
29	Andhra Pradesh	84665533	16933	12522	2822	1570	705	167	169	58	23	17
30	Karnataka	61130704	12226	8143	2037	2193	509	325	122	146	30	27
31	Goa	1457723	291	172	48	19	12	05	3	0	2	2
32	Lakshadweep #	64429	21	14	3	04	1	01	1	0	1	2
33	Kerala	33387677	6677	4575	1113	813	278	233	67	39	14	0
34	Tamil Nadu	72138958	14427	8706	2405	1283	601	256	144	232	32	39
35	Puducherry	1244464	248	53	41	24	10	03	2	0	4	0
36	A & N Islands#	379944	126	114	19	19	05	04	1	0	3	3

* Required; ** Existing; # Hilly tribal areas

Table-2: Public health workforce required in the country

S. No.	Workforce	Required	S. No.	Workforce	Required
01	Hospital superintendent	3631	41	Dietician	3631
02	Medical specialist	9684	42	PFT technician	1211
03	General Surgeon	19766	43	OT technician	10082
04	Physician	10082	44	Counselor	13713
05	Orthopedic an	4842	45	Cyto technician	1211
06	Dermatologist	3631	46	Lady Health Visitor	31457
07	Ophthalmologist	4842	47	Public health nurse	10082
08	Obstetrician & Gynecologist	22188	48	Nurse	407440
09	Pediatrics	19766	49	Sister in charge	12100
10	Anesthetist	20977	50	General duty workers/ hospital attendants	50840
11	Radiologist	4842	51	Sanitary worker	18165
12	Radiotherapist	1211	52	ANM	488888
13	PMR specialist	1211	53	Health workers	282354
14	Microbiologist	1211	54	Health assistants	80664
15	Eye surgeon	12502	55	Ophthalmic assistants	54045
16	ENT surgeon	1211	56	Dental assistant	16133
17	Dental Surgeon	14924	57	Dental technician/hygienist	7262
18	General Duty Medical Officer	106492	58	Matron	3631
19	Part time Cancer Surgeon/Physician	10082	59	Assistant matron	1211
20	Pathologist	4842	60	Rehabilitation worker	57676
21	Pathologist cum blood bank in charge	1211	61	Clerk	80664
22	Psychiatrist	3631	62	Data handler	62916
23	Clinical psychologist	1211	63	Laboratory technician	87522
24	General Duty Medical Officer of AYUSH	10082	64	Dresser	20164
25	Specialist of AYUSH	57676	65	Ward boys	50410
26	Forensic officer	3631	66	Sweepers	50410
27	Public health Manager	13713	67	Chowkidars	50410
28	Physiotherapist/ OT	4842	68	Dhobi	10082
29	Rehabilitation therapist	1211	69	Mali	10082
30	Prosthetics	1211	70	Aya	50410
31	Orthotics	1211	71	OPD attendant	10082
32	Accounts manager	50414	72	Registration Clerk	20164
33	Pharmacist	88733	73	Peon	20164
34	Radiographer	31057	74	Driver	70578
35	Radiotherapy technician	242	75	Cold chain and logistics assistant	54045
36	Dark room assistant	1211	76	Psychiatric social worker/ medical social worker	1211
37	ECG technician	3631	77	Instructor for young hearing impaired	1211
38	ECHO technician	1211	78	Plumber	1211
39	Audiometric an	1211	79	Cold chain handler	1211
40	Audiometric technician	2420	80	Class IV	161328

Table-1: Deficiencies in number of facilities

S. No.	Staff	Existing	S. No.	Staff	Existing
1.	Doctors	25870	10.	Radiographers	1817
2.	Surgeons	1531	11.	Pharmacist	21688
3.	Ayush	8900	12.	Lab Technician	15094
4.	O & G	1939	13.	BEE	3063
5.	Physician	1165	14.	Nursing staff	58450
7.	Pediatrician	1311	15.	Health workers	244231
8.	Specialists	6781	16.	Health assistants	33599
9.	GDMO	9933			

Sources: RHS Bulletin 2009

References:

1. GOI, MOHFW. "Mission documents on NRHM 2005-12." *Ministry of health and family welfare, Govt. of India*. April 2005. www.mohfw.nic.in/nrhm (accessed May 2010).
2. MOHFW. "IPHS_for_SUBCENTRES.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
3. MOHFW. "IPHS_for_PHC.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
4. MOHFW. "IPHS_for_DH.pdf" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2006. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
5. MOHFW. "IPHS for 51 to 100 bedded with Comments of Subgroup" *Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India*. 2007. www.mohfw.nic.in (accessed June 7, 2009).
6. Ministry of health & FW, Government of India "Rural Health Survey Bulletins" 2006, 2008"
7. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India "MIS on NRHM 2010".
8. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India "Reports of Common review mission (CRMs)". www.mohfw.nic.in/crms (accessed July 2010).
9. "New cadre in health sector of the country." *All India Applied Sociology Subject Association*. 2010. www.aissa.co.in (accessed 2010).
10. Sharma, Rohan. *The country needs additional seven lakh doctors*. Reviews, New-Delhi: All India, Applied Sociology Subject Association, 2010.
11. "Training strategy under NRHM." *Ministry of health and family welfare, Govt. of India*. 2009. www.mohfw.nic.in/nrhm (accessed 2010).
